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Peak Caller: A Peak Calling Algorithm for DNase-seq Data

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Abstract: With the development of bioinformatics, the performance of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology is also improving. Peak detection is always a very active field in NGS, because the success of data analysis largely depends on the accuracy of peak detection. based on the characteristics of existing peak detection technology, in this paper we developed a peak detection algorithm for DNase-seq data analysis. The process of PeakCaller algorithm mainly includes the following three stages: 1) data preprocessing; 2) data analysis, which is specifically divided into a) detecting the genomic location of dnase-seq data, b) using gaussian convolution to trim configuration data, c) determining candidate peaks, and d) determining DHSS peaks; 3) algorithm performance evaluation. PeakCaller algorithm is a peak detection algorithm for DNase-seq data. PeakCaller is written in Python3. the algorithm is open source and available at: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/peakcaller1/>

Keywords: Next-Generation Sequencing; DNase-seq; Peak calling; Peak calling Algorithms.

1. Introduction

Since the development of the first algorithm for sequence alignment by Wunsch and Needleman in 1970 [1] and the appearance of novel approaches such as NGS technologies at the end of the 1990s. This has led to the rapid development of bioinformatics, which combines computer science, mathematics, and statistics to study and benefit from the processing and analysis of biological data.

With the remarkable development in recent years in the field of bioinformatics, NGS techniques are becoming more readily available to analyze genome data with more accurate performance.

In practical applications, various peak detection algorithms have been developed for the next generation sequencing technology. Each algorithm has its own characteristics and limitations.

For example, MACS, one of the earliest peak detection algorithms, detects the peaks in chip-seq data based on the poisson distribution. The algorithm was proposed by Yong Zhang and Tao Liu et al. in 2008. F-seq is a software package used to generate continuous marker sequence density estimation, which can identify sites of biological significance. Its output can be displayed directly in the UCSC genome browser. The algorithm was developed by Alan p. Boyle et al. in 2008. CisGenome is used for FDR (false discovery rate) peak recognition. CisGenome has two features: single chain filtering method and boundary refinement method. The algorithm was proposed by Hong kai Ji et al. in 2008. The PePr method applies the negative binomial distribution (NBD) and local variance estimation process to the differential binding location detection in chip-seq experiment. This method was proposed by Yanxiao Zhang et al. in 2014.

2. Related work

In practice, there are many diverse peak calling algorithms developed for NGS technologies and each algorithm has its own methods and requirements. MACS [2] is one of earliest algorithms for peak calling which presented in 2008 by Yong Zhang and Tao Liu et al, MACS is one of the oldest peak caller used for detect peaks for ChIP-seq data which uses a Poisson distribution. MACS available at (<https://github.com/taoliu/MACS/>). F-Seq [3] was published by Alan P. Boyle et al in 2008. F-Seq was developed for summarizing DNase-seq data in regions of the genome, it has also used to identify peak from ChIP-seq data. F-Seq uses a nonparametric statistics KDE to show genomics features of interest across the genome. Hongkai Ji, et al. [4] introduced CisGenome in 2008. CisGenome is a set of methods for analyzing ChIP-seq data. CisGenome utilized FOR (The false discovery rate) to Identify peaks. There are two main features in CisGenome single-strand filtering options and boundary refinement. In 2014, Yanxiao Zhang, et al. present a PePr peak-caller for detecting differential binding positions in ChIP-Seq experiments. PePr method read amounts across the genome among biological models by a negative binomial distribution (NBD) and application a local variance estimation process. Ritornello [5] was published by Kelly P. Stanton, et al. in 2017. Ritornello a peak calling method for finding TF-binding sites in ChIP-seq. Ritornello was programmed in C++ using the FFTW compiler. Additional analysis and graphics were made by using the R language. BinQuasi [6] was published by Emily Goren, et al. in 2018. The Proposed algorithm BinQuasi is a peak caller algorithm for ChIP-seq data. BinQuasi software available in R package.

After providing a detailed introduction on these previously published peak calling algorithms, here we can summarize their characteristic. Variations in the feature of the algorithms make

them detect a different set of peaks for the same dataset. Generally, peak calling algorithms can be conceptually described based on the following basic attributes: 1) Read shifting; 2) Background estimation; 3) Identifying peaks; 4) Significance analysis; 5) Redundancies removal.

3. Overview of The Next-Generation Sequencing and Peak calling

NGS (Next-Generation Sequencing) technologies have been useful to many scientific and clinical areas including detection of genetic variations. Recent developments in the NGS have allowed researchers and scientists to study a variety of molecular events active on the genome with high accuracy [7]. Extensive peak calling algorithms for NGS data demonstrate the evolving and diverse needs of the research community. The chromatin-based NGS techniques such as Chip-seq, DNase-seq, MNase-seq ...etc, have been recognized and adopted by various research projects. DNase I hypersensitive regions sequencing (DNase-Seq) is a technique which depends on a firm DNase I footprinting protocol [8]. This technique is a widely used method for profiling cis-regulatory components in open chromatin areas. ChIP-seq (Chromatin Immunoprecipitation Followed by NGS) is one of the widely used techniques for the genome-wide locations of DNA binding proteins such as transcription factors (TF) or modified histones [7, 9, 10]. MNase-seq is a technique in which micrococcal nuclease digestion of chromatin is followed by NGS to determine the locations of high nucleosome occupancy [10, 11]. In 2013 a new technique as a complementary to MNase-seq called ATAC (Transposase-Attainable Chromatin by Sequencing) was introduced to study chromatin accessibility [12]. Advances in these techniques varied between experimental approaches and computational approaches. Peak calling method is generally the first step in the analysis of these data [13].

Recently, there are more than 30 peak calling algorithms for the NGS data have been developed as of now. Most of these algorithms are developed for the ChIP-seq data analysis. Generally, most peak callers are based on the negative binomial model, Poisson model or KDE (Kernel Density Estimator) to address the count data. For example, MACS uses a Poisson model to test the significance of tag enrichment adjusting the local mapping structure [2]; ZINBA applies a KDE to estimate local read density and identifies enriched areas [14], etc. The number of literature increasingly grows, which keeps enriching our understanding of the experimental data. The algorithms that are developed to detect peaks (or identify peaks) are called peak callers, peak detectors, peak finder.

DNase-Seq Data Analysis and peak calling experiments:

DNase-seq is a technique which study and analysis the enzyme which splits duplex DNA in human and animals, and the function of this key enzyme is to manage the residues of the nuclease [15]. The overall goal of peak calling in DNase-seq experiment is to find genomic locations. Also Peak detection in DNase-seq analysis, is the process to find genomic positions in which reads pile up to form pulse shapes. Figure 1 shows the workflow for analyzing and peak calling DNase-seq.

Figure 1: Workflow for analyzing and peak calling DNase-seq

4. METHODOLOGY

In the previous part of the paper, we introduced an overview of the fundamental of next-generation sequencing data and algorithms that used for identifying the peak in some techniques like ChIP-seq, MNase-seq, and FAIRE-seq ...etc. The purpose of this paper is to peak calling algorithm for DNase-seq data.

Datasets

The DNase-seq data used in this study was downloaded BED format from <http://hgdownload.cse.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeOpenChromDnase/>, and [\(http://hgdownload.soe.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeRegDnaseClusterd/\)](http://hgdownload.soe.ucsc.edu/goldenPath/hg19/encodeDCC/wgEncodeRegDnaseClusterd/) these data produced by the ENCODE. This Data are clusters from single cell types.

Development PeakCaller algorithm for DNase-seq data analysis

Overview of the algorithm:

In this section, an overview of the proposed methods used to analysis DNase-seq data. PeakCaller is developed Based on the formal methodologies of data analysis on the Next generation sequencing. We developed our new method steps for a PeakCaller method including the following steps. Algorithm 1 shows the workflow of PeakCaller and Figure 2 shows the flowchart of PeakCaller, which consist of three steps:

- 1) Data preprocessing.
- 2) Analyzing data :
 - Detection genome position for DNase-seq data.
 - Smoothing profile data by using Gaussian convolution
 - Identification of the candidates.
 - Identification peaks of DHSs (*Algorithm 2* and *listing 1* show how to identifying peaks).
- 3) The final report.

Data preprocessing:

Before analyzing data or peak detection using multiple peak calling programs, the following steps apply to the raw dataset:

First step: the raw data aligned to the reference genome by using any alignment programs like Bowtie [16]. In our experiments we did not need this process because we used data after processing It is not raw data we downloaded it from the ENCODE website. But if the data is raw you will need the previous steps to align the reads to alignment data.

Smoothing profile data:

To smooth DNase I HS profile we used Gaussian convolution as equation (4. 1).

$$y(x) = f(x) * g(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \sum_{k=x-3\sigma}^{x+3\sigma} f(k) e^{-\frac{(x-k)^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad (4. 1)$$

Where x is a genome coordinate, $f(x)$ for the DNase I HS site at coordinate x , $y(x)$ is the smoothing at coordinate x and the scope $(x - 3\sigma)$, $(x + 3\sigma)$ is used for a smooth profile. And also σ is used to smooth the borders adjustment.

Figure 2: A flowchart of PeakCaller.

Identification the candidates peaks

By using P-value of Poisson approximation choosing and sorting peaks based on the shape of the peaks and make a comparison between different peaks (Listing 1) shows identify peaks. This step are established in the equation (3. 2) and the code shows in listing 1.

$$p(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = 0, j = 1 \\ p(i), & \text{if } i \geq 1, j = i + 1, \\ 1 - p(i) & \text{if } i \geq 1, j = i - 1, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3. 2)$$

Algorithm 2. algorithm for identify peaks

INPUT : N are number of DNase-seq reads, I, R_i = 1

Require: $tags(I - n)$

OUTPUT : List of Peaks

```
1:   $j$  (number of Peaks from DNase reads),  $T$  (threshold)
2:  for  $I = 1$  to  $N$  do
3:    align read  $R_i$  on the genome
4:    Stock the mapping information
5:  End if
6:   $i \leftarrow 1$ 
7:  Add(peak $i$ , tag $1$ )
8:  For all tag $\square$  in strand where  $j > 1$ 
9:    do
10:   If  $start(tag\square) \leq end(tag\square - 1)$  then
11:     add(peak $i$ , tag $\square$ )
12:   else
13:     Pass
14:   end for
15: return peaks
Ensure: final result.
```

Let $R_i = \{R_1, R_2, R_3, \dots, R_N\}$ denote a set of align reads from DNase-seq data with read $R_i \in \sum^j$, where N the number of reads, and j denotes the number of peaks from DNase-seq experiment.

Implementation:

PeakCaller software has been implemented in Python version 3.

Listing 1 : list shows how to identify peaks

```
def identifying_peaks (self):
```

```
    self.identify_peak = { }
```

```
    self.content_peak = { }
```

```
    First_peak = [ 'left_end_peak', 'max_begin_left', 'max_end_right', 'start_right',
'left_end_peak_index', 'max_begin_left_index', 'max_begin_right_index', 'start_right_index', 'serial_no'
]
```

```
    peak_terminated = 'none'
```

```
    catch1 = 0
```

```
    up_down = 0
```

```

serial_no = 0

for x in range ( 1, len (self.result_table ) ) :

    if self.rise_list [x] > 0 :

        #\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\ Record the start of the first peak\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\\

        if up_down == 0:

            first_peak[0] = self.result_table [x][0]

            first_peak[4] = x

        elif up_down == 1:

            first_peak [1] = 'max_begin_left'

            first_peak[5] = 'max_begin_left_index'

        elif up_down == -1:

            if type ( first_peak [ 3 ] ) != int or type ( first_peak[7] ) != int :

                first_peak[3] = self.result_table[x-1][0]

                first_peak[7] = x-1

            peak_terminated = first_peak[:]

            First_peak = ['left_end_peak', 'max_begin_left', 'max_end_right', 'start_right',
'left_end_peak_index', 'max_begin_left_index', 'max_begin_right_index',
'start_right_index', 'serial_no']

            first_peak[0] = self.result_table[x][0]

            first_peak[4] = t

            up_down = 1

            catch1 = 0

        elif self.rise_list [x] < 0:

            if up_down == -1:

                first_peak[3] = 'start_right'

                first_peak[7] = 'max_begin_right_index'

            elif up_down == 1:

                first_peak[2] = self.result_table[x-catch1][0]

                first_peak[6] = x-catch1

                if type(first_peak[1])!= int or type(first_peak[5])!=int:

                    first_peak[1] = self.result_table[x-max(1,catch1)][0]

```

```

        first_peak[5] = x-max(1,catch1)

up_down = -1

catch1 = 0

elif self.rise_list[x] == 0:

    catch1=catch1+1

    if up_down == 1 and self.rise_list[x-1]>0:

        first_peak[1] = self.result_table[x][0]

        first_peak[5] = x

    elif up_down == -1 and self.rise_list[x-1] < 0 :

        first_peak[3] = self.result_table [x-1][0]

        first_peak[7]=x-1

if x==len(self.result_table)-1:

    if self.rise_list[x]<0:

        if up_down== -1:

            if type (first_peak[3]) != int or type(first_peak[7]) != int:

                first_peak[3] = self.result_table [x][0]

                first_peak[7] = x

        peak_terminated = first_peak [:]

        if peak_terminated!='none' and type(peak_terminated) == list and type(peak_terminated [0] )
== int and type(peak_terminated[1]) == int and type(peak_terminated[2]) == int and
type(peak_terminated[3])==int and type ( peak_terminated[4])==int and type(peak_terminated[5]) ==
int and type ( peak_terminated[6]) == int and type(peak_terminated[7]) == int and
type(peak_terminated[8]) == int:

            serial_no = serial_no + 1

            peak_terminated[8] = serial_no

            self.identify_peak[serial_no] = peak_terminated

            for z in range(peak_terminated[4], peak_terminated [7] + 1):

                self.content_peak[z] = peak_terminated

            peak_terminated = 'none'

print('\t testing ....> Top peak serial number: ', serial_no)

print(' detection for peaks is finished.', '\t', time.strftime('%y-%m-%d %A %H:%M:%S',
time.localtime()))

```

```
print('\t testing ....> The number of peaks: ', len(self.identify_peak))
```

Command line options

Table 1. PeakCaller Command line options

-h	help	Display help options and exit.
-i	Input File	For input file data with BED format
-o	Output File	Output files data, the output of software is
--version	version	Display version information and exit.


```
hamdan@hamdan-VirtualBox: ~/Downloads
hamdan@hamdan-VirtualBox:~/Downloads$ python3 peak_calling.py -h

A peak calling program to detect peak from DNase-seq data.
The program need python3 to run
Usage: peak_calling.py -i /path/inputfile -o /path/outputfile -c chromosome_name
-l chromosome_length

Options:
--version          show program's version number and exit
-h, --help        show this help message and exit
-i IP_FILE, --input=IP_FILE
                  "/path/filename" inputfile of single-end sequencing
                  tags in a standard BED Format (chromosome <tab> start
                  <tab> end <tab> name <tab> score <tab> strand).
-o OP_FILE, --output=OP_FILE
                  "/path/filename" The program will output two result
                  files.
-c CHROMOSOME_NAME, --chromosome_name=CHROMOSOME_NAME
                  Specify the name of the chromosome
-l CHROMOSOME_LENGTH, --chromosome_length1=CHROMOSOME_LENGTH
                  The length of chromosome specified by parameter "--c"
                  or "--chromosome_name"
```

Figure 3: A Screenshot of the peakcaller program shows help option

The PeakCaller progress messages and the output files generated by the software, as shown in Figure 3. The message begins with an explanatory text about the use of the input data and how to specify the output folder. And Figure 4 shows a Screenshot of the PeakCaller program shows how to run and analysis data.

```

hamdan@hamdan-VirtualBox: ~/Downloads
<tab> end <tab> name <tab> score <tab>
strand).
-o OP_FILE, --output=OP_FILE
"/path/filename" The program will out
put two result
files.
-c CHROMOSOME_NAME, --chromosome_name=CHROMOSOME_NAME
Specify the name of the chromosome
-l CHROMOSOME_LENGTH, --chromosome_length1=CHROMOSOME_LENGTH
The length of chromosome specified by p
arameter "--c"
or "--chromosome_name"
hamdan@hamdan-VirtualBox:~/Downloads$ python3 peak_calling.py
-i/home/hamdan/Downloads/chipseq.bed -o/home/hamdan/Desktop/ou
tput

A peak calling program to detect peak from DNase-seq data.
The program need python3 to run
start preprocessing data ...

reading initial data: /home/hamdan/Downloads/chipseq.bed
data storage locaion : /home/hamdan/Desktop/output/
data row:1965192

```

Figure 4: A Screenshot of the PeakCaller program shows how to run and analysis data

5. RESULTS

Overview of the PeakCaller

PeakCaller is a software written in python language is peak calling software for analysis DNase-Seq data. Is based on a simple methodology, so applies a GSK for smoothing data and apply Poisson model for identify peaks.

Peak calling by PeakCaller on DNase-seq data

Using software PeakCaller, we identified 430,558 peaks. The peak distribution through all the genome was then used to analyze the distribution of gene correlated to DHSs. We downloaded the DNase datasets from ENCODE (University of Washington) (<https://genome.ucsc.edu/cgi-bin/hgTrackUi?db=hg19&g=wgEncodeUwDnase>).

Figure 5: Distribution of Dnase I hypersensitive (DHS) peaks detected by the PeakCaller on the whole genome and per chromosome.

Figure 6: Proportion of DNase I hypersensitive peaks in each chromosome.

Figure 5 shows the distribution of Dnase I hypersensitive (DHS) peaks detected by the PeakCaller on the whole genome and per chromosome. Also through Figure 6 we observe that each chromosome in the DNase I hypersensitive is linked to an initial peak. A comparatively high rate of first peaks associated on DHSs was determined by PeakCaller on chromosomes chr1, chr10, chr12, 14, and chrX.

Comparison PeakCaller with other algorithms

Several methods that combine different approaches have been proposed for analyzing NGS data. In this study, we used Two Type of NGS data are DNase-seq and Chip-seq. in this study we used the MACS algorithm and SISRrs Peak-Finder for comparison with PeakCaller.

Figure 7: Comparison of the number of detected peaks by the PeakCaller with the MACS and SISRrs algorithms for DNase-seq data.

We used the MACS algorithm which is the best algorithm for analyzing ChIP-seq data and SISRrs Peak-Finder for comparison with our algorithm. The result of the comparison is presented in Figure 7. We conducted DNase-seq experiments for peak calling from 247,186,832 chromosomes and identified 91,492 peaks with the PeakCaller algorithm. Less results have been observed by comparisons to the Macs algorithm. We infer from this that the performance of the PeakCaller algorithm is the best in the analysis of DNase-seq data compared to the famous peak-calling algorithms.

In Figure 8, we present the results obtained from the comparison PeakCaller with the MACS and SISRrs algorithms by using Chip-seq data. Although the PeakCaller algorithm was developed for the analysis DNase-seq data, but after we analysis the Chip-seq data we found that it gave good results compared to the Chip-seq data analysis algorithms. PeakCaller called a large number of peaks in both DNase-seq and Chip-seq, while MACS called an extremely large number of peaks only in Chip-seq and few numbers of peaks from DNase-seq data. Therefore, the PeakCaller algorithm is the best algorithm for DNase-seq data analysis.

Figure 8: Comparison of the number of detected peaks by PeakCaller with the MACS and SISR algorithms for Chip-seq data.

We compared our PeakCaller algorithm with peak calls from SISR and MACS by changing the threshold value every experiment to identify Broad peaks from DNase-seq data.

Figure 9 Comparison of the number of detected broad peaks by the PeakCaller with the MACS and SISR for a series of values of threshold.

For the show the differences among the results of PeakCaller algorithm with the results acquired from each peak caller, the number of peaks identified by each peak caller and PeakCaller algorithm detected the more peaks by comparing with MACS and SISR from DNase-seq experiment Using different reads in each experiment (Threshold= 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1) and the results are shown in Figure 3.10. And the result of the number of peaks detected by PeakCaller, MACS and SISR are shown in table 8.

Performance of PeakCaller algorithm:

In order to test the performance of the PeakCaller algorithm. We ran PeakCaller with two different data, DNase-seq and ChIP-seq data. PeakCaller with default setting takes about 6 minutes on a 2.8 GHz CPU to analysis from more than 6 million reads.

Figure 3.11 Comparison of the running time of the PeakCaller with other algorithms

In Figure 3.11, we present the result comparison of the running time of the PeakCaller with the MACS and SISSRs algorithms. By comparing the algorithm of PeakCaller with other algorithms, we found that the time complexity is lower than other algorithms.

6. Conclusion

With the rapid progression of NGS technologies, the peak calling algorithms is constantly developing. Currently, several peak calling algorithms are available for the identification regions in a genome, these regions are those where DNA interacts with protein. But the peak calling algorithms has not yet grown to a point where it can be applied to more than one type of data (i.e. ChIP-seq, MNase-seq, DNase-seq, etc.) and to different formats data (i.e. SAM, BAM, GFF etc.). Although there are some algorithms applicable to other techniques, they are still deficient in some aspects. Recently, DNase-seq and ChIP-seq techniques have been extensively used to map TF binding sites on a genome-wide [17]. But currently, if we compare between ChIP-seq analysis technique and DNase-seq analysis technique we will find there is a lack of DNase-seq analysis programs, especially in the peak finding programs. So many researcher have utilized ChIP-seq peak-calling tools for analysis DNase-seq data. Few developed a specific peak-calling tool for the DNase-seq data.

In this paper, we have proposed a PeakCaller algorithm for DNase-seq data analysis. In this algorithm, we detect peaks with the LOG method and smoothing data with the Gaussian smoothing. The peaks are identified with the following standards: 1) the peaks width must be from 80 to 250 DHSs; 2) the P value; 3) threshold is 0.08 for very experience.

To test the performance of the PeakCaller algorithm, we compare Macs and SISR algorithms. For comparison, it used two NGS data, DNase -seq and Chip-seq. On a 2.8GHz CPU, it takes about six minutes for the default PeakCaller to perform more than 6 million read analyses. In the analysis of DNase-seq data, PeakCaller, as a peak detection algorithm, has significantly improved the number and time complexity of peak detection compared with MACS and SISR algorithms that currently perform the best in chip-seq data peak detection.

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